

WHY IS IT HARD TO BE DIFFERENT?

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Abstract:

The aim of the article titled "Why is it difficult to be different?" is to analyze the matter of "Living rights and educational rights of the disabled students", which is hushed up although frequently witnessed in our living quarters, through a real life scenario. It also aims to emphasize that it is necessary to identify the responsible ones for the problems experienced by autistic students and their families and the situation caused by those who are reported in news in the printed media, and to point out enforcement of laws thereof. In this article, descriptive survey method was used as a method. The concepts of booing, autistic, student and scandal in Aksaray are discussed after searching for them in newspapers, websites and television news. As evidenced in the recent incident in Turkey, the lack of primary-school inclusive educational support in mainstream education services is a major drawback. The effects of the said drawback are amplified by the inadequate knowledge and experience of the teachers who are assigned therein regarding the education of children with disabilities, and their negative attitudes. The school principal and his assistant, who were responsible for the booing of autistic students in Aksaray, are dismissed from their administrative positions. Mukhtar, Director of National Education, Governor, and Minister of National Education may have difficulty to perform their duties with peace of mind and a clear conscience after this event. Thereafter, such events will happen again, but the officers will be worried about being dismissed.

Keywords: autistic, Aksaray, autistic student, booing

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1. Introduction

The aims of this study are to identify those who are responsible for the situation that autistic students and their families have found themselves in because of a certain news published on media which is an example of the problem of “the right to education for people with disabilities” that has been frequently experienced in recent years but was always covered, and to point out to the need for the implementation of the relevant laws. According to the results of “People with Disabilities in Turkey Survey” conducted in 2002 by State Institute of Statistics and Prime Ministry Administration of People with Disabilities, the ratio of people with disabilities to the total population is 12.29% in Turkey (Özer, 2013). It is seen in the general population with a frequency of 1-3%. There are many reasons, especially genetic anomalies (World Health Organization, 2007). It usually gives close to 3% results. There are approximately seven million intellectually disabled individuals in Turkey (MEB 2015). The rate of claiming the right to education in these individuals is 25.6%. Contrary to popular belief, the more people with disabilities can exercise their right to education, the happier those individuals and their families will be.

On November 11, 2009 a piece of news titled “*Autistic students were booed in Aksaray*” was published by a newspaper. While this was a small and unimportant news on the first day, it became necessary to identify the situation that occurred when social media, televisions and sensitive journalists chased after the event. Keeping this event on the news so that similar things don’t happen in other schools will enable inadequate students and their families to have established gains. What are the opinions of Grand National Assembly of Turkey Down Syndrome, Autism and Other Developmental Disorders Research Commission, Ministry of Education, Aksaray Governorship, Aksaray National Education Directorate, Istanbul Autism Volunteers Association, Aksaray Association for Solidarity with Children with Autism, Anadolu Autism Foundation, parents with autistic children, Laleli neighborhood local authority, and lastly AKP Spokesman Ömer Çelik in this situation? What needs to be done?

Students included in inclusive education have the opportunity to be with their peers in the social life and education process. This association is important for students with insufficient academic, daily life and social skills as it enables them to take other children as role models. Experiences shared with other children in a social environment provide a basis for students with special needs to learn what the society expects of them as individuals and teaches them to respond to these expectations. It is observed that individuals with special needs are successful in the educational arrangements in the least restricted environments (Saylan G., Pekçağlıyan N., 2002).

Inclusion is defined as “*educational environments developed to enable individuals who require special education to interact with other individuals and to achieve their educational objectives at the highest level*”. While these definitions determine what should be in the theoretical framework, the case study proves that it is not realized at the desired level during application. The case study was reported in a newspaper with the headline “*Autistic students were booed*” on November 7, 2019.

Examining this news in detail reveals that it is necessary to discuss what kind of instinct lies behind the efforts of those responsible for enforcing the law, not just in our state and bureaucracy but also in other countries, to protect certain individuals or certain other things. For this reason, three different cases and the efforts of people with management responsibilities to conceal these cases and try to make it look like they didn't happen at all will be discussed.

2. Method

In this paper, qualitative case study methodology was applied by searching newspapers, TV news records, and the internet with the keywords: "booing", "autistic students", and "scandal in Aksaray" (Gürbüz S., Şahin F., 2016).

3. Discussion

Drawing attention to the situation in a country by using a few of the tens of developments happening everyday carries the risk of simplifying the situation. However, in cases such as this which special education students had to go through, a couple of events or developments can strikingly show the situation in the country and in the society. The "events" listed below do not only mirror social, political, economic and "moral" destruction and decay, they also point to the inevitability of such developments that have proliferated under the conditions of capitalist exploitation. The three events and the effort to conceal these three events from the public are common. Those who conceal are those who have responsibility. The effort to design society through the media becomes more evident in such events. The Chernobyl disaster may happen in another country, but it concerns us too. There are counts of rapes in the cult houses that provide shelter for the children of poor families for educational purposes and this has always been hidden. When the suicide incidents with cyanide occurred, the Director of Communication blocked all communication.

Case study 1: In the spring of 1986, there was an apocalypse with the explosion of a reactor at the Chernobyl Nuclear Power Plant in Ukraine. Unfortunately, the radiation effects of the event, which is known as the biggest disaster caused by humanity in the history of the world are still continuing. Leaks cause radiation sickness. Disaster was initially hidden by the Ukrainian authorities. They admitted that the reactor exploded 2 days after the explosion. Even the Soviet Union, of which Ukraine was a part at that time, did not know about the accident. About 600.000-800.000 workers and firemen from all over the Soviet Union came to the rescue. The Soviet Union worked for 2 years to extinguish the fire, and to bury radioactive equipment, houses and warehouses. They even wrapped the radioactive material around the graves. Many of these people either died, became disabled or committed suicide. Although only 31 deaths were reported during the incident, most deaths occurred after radiation. More than 6.000 cases of thyroid cancer have been reported as a result of radiation exposure. Due to the fear of indeterminate radiation poisoning, many doctors advised pregnant women to have an

abortion to avoid having a disabled child (<https://onedio.com/>). After the Chernobyl disaster, discussions about radiation started in our country. Carried with the wind and rain, the radiation spoiled a lot of agricultural products, especially the tea plants. Despite this fact, the Minister of Customs and Monopolies at the time claimed that the tea was cancer free by drinking tea on TV.

Case study 2: This event happened on Sunday, March 4, 2016 and was on the news on March 13. A teacher in Karaman allegedly raped at least 45 boys in sect houses. The teacher who raped 9 – 10 years old boys who were allegedly staying in homes rented by people close to Ensar Foundation and Karaman Anatolian Imam Hatip and Imam Hatip High School Alumni and Members Association (KAIMDER) was arrested. M.B. was a class teacher working in a school in Karaman city center who gave private lessons to students staying in sect houses. M. B. raped students in various houses where he went for private lessons. The incident was heard when a student told about the rape to his family. M.B. was arrested by the court and sent to prison. The prosecutor's office made the case confidential. Another teacher was assigned to the school where the arrested class teacher M.B. was working. After the teacher was arrested, 8 students went to Karaman State Hospital with their families on March 6. The children were checked, and findings of rape were documented. Karaman Provincial Director of National Education Asim Sultanoğlu said *“The information that the teacher was arrested is correct. However, it would not be right to give detailed information about the file that has a confidentiality decision. We launched an administrative investigation”*. The Public Prosecutor's Office, which conducted the investigation, made a 'confidentiality' decision for the file containing medical reports about the students who were allegedly raped. While the judicial investigation was continuing, the Directorate of National Education also launched an administrative investigation against the teacher M. B. It was stated that Muammer B. had been working at Gazi Mustafa Kemal Primary School, one of the best schools in the city center, for 3 years, and volunteered in the studies opened by some foundations and associations for students. While the arrest of a teacher in Karaman for the alleged rape of younger boys was shocking everyone in the city, the eyes were turned towards the houses opened by foundations and associations under the name of course and study. Karaman Governor Murat Koca said that the incident was a forensic case and the investigation was being conducted by the judicial authorities and that there was a confidentiality decision about the case, and it would be more convenient for Chief Public Prosecutor's Office to make a public statement. Head of Karaman Anatolian Imam Hatip and Imam Hatip High School Alumni and Members Association (KAIMDER) Mehmet Sarı stated that they are not involved with any house or dormitory. He said *“M. B. does not have any membership or registration with us. We do not have any house or a house business. We are only in contact with imam hatip schools”* (cumhuriyet.com.tr).

Case study 3: Director of Communications of Republic of Turkey said in his statement to AA that one child and two adults were found dead in a house in Bakırköy, İstanbul and this deeply shocked everyone. Reminding that the investigation about the incident was still being carried out by the Bakırköy Chief Public Prosecutor's Office, the director said that the statements other than those made by the prosecutor's office and

other official institutions carrying out the relevant studies should not be respected. He stated *“Explaining this and similar cases that has happened recently with the concepts of ‘mass suicide’ or ‘suicide’ is very misleading and strays us away from the solution. As in the previous examples, using the concept of ‘mass suicide’ in this event legitimizes the massacre and creates the perception that it is an event that must be met with understanding”*. The director pointed out that the incident was not only suicidal and that it is clear from the statements of the previous prosecution statements that innocent people, spouses and children fell victim to mass murder by drinking poison and added, *“As such, making murderers who committed suicide after killing their children and wives seem innocent or desperate makes all murders ordinary and innocent. Therefore, the language we use during such events can have negative effects such as causing the appearance of similar cases and making them look socially ordinary”*. Emphasizing that important responsibilities fall on every part of the society in this regard, the Director stated that the most important task belongs to media organizations and employees who inform the public. Reminding that the Directorate of Communication have published a 13-item document on issues that the media should pay attention in similar events, the Director said: *“In cases where such news is essential to be made, the method should not be mentioned, and the incident should be communicated with the simplest form and without any details. Suicide should never be glorified in any way and should not be presented as a bold behavior. Suicide news should not appear on the first pages of newspapers, headlines of websites, and on TV screens repeatedly with the words ‘flash news’”*. The issue should be approached similarly in the social media channels of media organizations. Massacres and suicides should not be shown as a method of solving people's problems, headings that center suicide and solution concepts should be avoided, and the language of news should be considered in this context. Especially, one of the worst examples of utilitarian approaches is the use of this painful incident by public figures and leaders as an irresponsible and out-of-place means of opposition. Everyone should be responsible for the social wounds and problems that everyday political venality will cause in such matters. Our state takes these and similar events very seriously and carries out the necessary work with all its institutions and organizations. As a society, we should support each other and become more united in such sensitive issues (aa.com.tr).

There are many more examples...

Here, families who take their autistic children to school were tried to be intimidated by an organization extending to the head of the school, head of the family union of the school, the neighborhood headman and the governor.

Spreading of the news: at the Central Mehmetçik Primary School in Aksaray, parents of the students demanded that the classes of students with autism to be closed. The parents came together at the school's departure time and booed the children with autism. After the incident was heard, the parents, the headman of the neighborhood and the school administration received strong negative reactions in social media (cumhuriyet.com.tr/).

First statement: Aksaray Governorship stated: *“The news titled ‘autistic children were booed in Aksaray’, which was published in some media organs, does not reflect the truth, and*

the children continue their normal education in their schools. In the 2020 investment program, a Special Education School with 12 classrooms has been planned and the necessary investigation has been initiated on the subject” (beyazgazete.com).

Second statement: Ministry of National Education launched an investigation on the subject. The ministry's statement said: *“An investigation was initiated by the inspectors of our Ministry regarding the incident reflected in the media with the title ‘Parents who want special education classes to be closed in Aksaray booted students with autism!’. Considering the sensitivities required by the special education class practice in our school in question, relevant arrangements have been made in the areas within the school, and education and training activities continue. Informative activities have been initiated by the experts of Aksaray Guidance Research Center for the parents about the special education students in the school” (birgun.net.).*

Third statement: Minister of National Education Ziya Selçuk said, *“The incident that hurt our children with autism and their families does not match with our education system or our social values.”* Speaking at the Training and Local Governments Workshop, Selçuk said, *“We have started the investigation process by sending a group of inspectors from Ankara”.* Selçuk noted the following, *“There are some problems that our children with autism experience in education. We are working on this. We are watching national and regional sensitivities during our work. I am carefully following what should be done in this regard. I know what should be done. We are working for our children who are continuing their education along their peers in the same classes in inclusive schools. There are new developments on this issue that we will announce to the public. We are doing a new study with a 6-million-euro budget to investigate the possibilities of Special Education. One of the topics we care the most about is awareness. I would like to state that we are in the process of transitioning to an inclusive system. We are following the issue carefully” (trthaber.com).*

Fourth statement: The head of the Laleli neighborhood, Şükrü Genç, said, *“I do not accept that I stirred up the citizens.”* and explained the tension that has been going on in the neighborhood, *“We are not against any disabled or mild autistic student. However, 17 students with severe autism came to the school recently. This has changed the situation. Their parents always have to be with them. We have separated the classes, but they have to see each other at the break. Those with severe autism are aged 14-16. This situation creates discomfort. Citizen are putting a lot of pressure on me.”* According to the news of BBC Turkey, Genç claimed that the parents are calling him every day to complain about the children with autism at the school, *“Citizens are putting a lot of pressure on me by complaining constantly. I discussed this with the Governor last week. The governor asked me to be patient for a month. I agreed and told the parents to be patient and wait for a month. The Provincial Director of National Education says it will take 8-9 months to solve this and further complicates the situation. The governor’s office said they would move the students to another school, but the citizens don’t believe this. That is because 3-4 years ago, citizens had complained about the same thing and the provincial director said they will transfer the students to another school, but they didn’t” (cumhuriyet.com.tr).*

Fifth statement: President of Istanbul Autism Volunteers Association Sedef Erken said: *“We don’t know what to think. These principals and teachers have been doing this for 10 years, not even one of them stood trial. The parents there eventually become the scapegoats. The head of the neighborhood and the principal of the school are the ones who planned this and provoked*

the parents. Even though their jobs are to prevent situations like this from happening, they do the opposite and provoke the parents into doing this impudence. This is not a simple neglect of duty any more, this is a crime against humanity". Stating that every kid has the right to education, Erken said, "Minister of Education should say 'These children have the right to education, I have their backs and I will hurt those who oppose!'. For years these projects have been funded by EU, trillions of euros have been spent. Those files are rotting in the archives of the Ministry of Education. As long as you don't teach the outputs of those projects to the principal in Aksaray, whatever you write in the legislation won't have any effect. The minister should support this. I will file a criminal complaint with the prosecutor's office about the minister for not doing his duty" (cumhuriyet.com.tr).

Sixth statement: Vice President of Aksaray Solidarity Association for Children with Autism, Cennet İnceöz said there were 352 students in the school and added "42 of them study in the special education class. A significant part of these are autistic. The principal of school was changed after the beginning of the term. Then there was a stir against autistic students. Then the situation escalated all the way to not letting the autistic children in the school. We met with the governor today. He said that an investigation has been launched against the principal and the head of the neighborhood". Stating that the principal, head of the neighborhood and head of the school family union provoked the parents into gathering in front of the school, İnceöz said, "They say that children with autism negatively affect their children's psychology. They say their children can't eat and can't sleep. About 50 parents booed the autistic students. Of course, there are also parents who are siding with us. Unfortunately, these children are not able to receive inclusive education under this condition" (sondakika.com).

Seventh statement: Barış Uluocak, Psychological Counseling and Guidance Teacher, emphasized that special students were being educated in the 'special education class' before and later they were included in the inclusive education. Uluocak said that thanks to this inclusive education, children with autism can start communicating with other children. Uluocak used the following statements regarding the incident at Mehmetçik Primary School: "Such discriminatory practices are seen against children with autism. It shows that the education system at this school is not well organized. Since parents focus on success and they are making education a race for students, they see special education students as obstacles. They are trying to remove their own children away from these children. We have to evaluate this problem in relation to the transformation in education. The children have forgotten about collectivity, solidarity, and co-production. Every child is chasing their own success story. Parents spend a lot of money on this. They see naughty children, children with autism, children with down syndrome, and children from foster homes as obstacles to the success of their own children. Liberalization in the education system in general has created this parent profile. They organize campaigns, try to send the children out of the classes, collect signatures, exclude children, etc. These children begin their lives with a disadvantage. Such behaviours increase their disadvantage and causes a lot of trouble for these children in current socio-political atmosphere" (sondakika.com).

Eighth statement: Cennet İnceöz, mother of an autistic child, explained that children with special needs have been discriminated against for a long time at Mehmetçik Primary School, but harassment has become unbearable from the beginning of the week:

“They have separated our children from the others with a screen in the classroom and our children can’t leave the classroom. Our children enter and leave the school through the back door, the dining halls are separate, the toilets are separate... Our children are prevented from interacting with other children. But for some reason they have switched to a total intimidation policy for the past few months. They’ve begun bullying our kids. Other parents began to insult the parents of children with autism. Some parents said, ‘Get out of here. We don’t want you. Our children’s psychology is negatively affected by your children’. They say that their kids are afraid of the autistic children, can’t eat, and have nightmares about them. They took the headman of the neighborhood with them and started to take action in the garden of the school, boo the mothers who went outside and insult them. It has been going on since the beginning of the week, we don’t know what to do”. İnceöz stated that these problems gradually increased with the start of the new education period and the change of school administration. İnceöz said “Some parents of children with autism had to take their children out of school. There were about 50 students in total in the classroom, but most parents took their child out of school as a result of these harassment and they no longer send them to any school. We had no such problems with the previous principal. With the beginning of the period, our principal has changed and these problems have started” (sondakika.com).

Ninth statement: Another parent, Nurcan Kara, stated that his nine-year-old daughter with autism has been attending Mehmetçik Primary School for three years, but the problems of discrimination and harassment have started only this year. Kara argues that children with autism in school get along well with other students, but parents are provoked by school management and the headman, *“With the filling of the new school administration, these children and their parents have been provoked against us. As far as we learned from other parents who supported us, the school administration said to some parents, ‘They will kick your children out of this school, they will build a new school for the autistic children.’. For this reason, they want our children gone. This is how they confront children and parents. When my child enrolled in this school, there were 40-50 students with autism, but now only 19 are attending school regularly. I learned that there is no demand for teachers from MEB despite the need for teachers. When I went to the Provincial Directorate of National Education, they said, ‘Your school did not request teachers.’. My child has friends with whom she got along and held hands. There are video records of this. The teacher she had been together and made great progress with for two years has been replaced this year. I said that our children have a separate connection with their teachers and that they could not cope with this situation. I asked for my child to be transferred to the class of the teacher she was used to, but the principal did not accept it. My daughter has come a long way in last three years, she has become social, but she wants her own teacher. The principal is aware of this situation but says her teacher won’t be back, he doesn’t need new teachers and the situation will continue like this. In this case, there is no point in my child attending this school. We have no academic expectation and our priority is behavioral progress and happiness”. Parents with children with autism also claim that the headman of Laleli District, Şükrü Genç, provoked other parents who gathered for protest in front of the school against students with autism, and that this is also present in the video recordings. Nurcan Kara states that the number of children with severe autism who have begun attending the school recently is four (sondakika.com).*

Tenth statement: Parin Yakupyan, Chairman of the Board of Special Children Education and Solidarity Association (ÖÇED), states that separating and isolating children with autism from other students, as in Mehmetçik Primary School, will bring various problems. According to Yakupyan, both the children with special needs and their families should be able to fully obtain the rights set out in the law, *“When children with autism were in the classroom, other parents and their children booed them and they heard this. According to Article 122 of the Turkish Criminal Code, this attitude is a direct discrimination. One of the parents there said, ‘What can you do if autistic children throw our children out of the window?’. Children with autism may have behavioral problems, but these problems fade away when they get the right education. They are not monsters; their hearts are filled with love. Families suffer a major trauma when their children are diagnosed with autism and they try to gain their right to education right afterwards. These children will develop if they can live in parallel with the society. But if the society rejects them, these children who already have communication problems will be affected deeply. Our voice is very loud in this example, but there are a lot of similar incidents where our voice is not as loud. Currently 1 in every 59 children is diagnosed with autism. They say it has increased to 1 in every 40 children. People who don’t want the children with autism in the same classroom as their own children today may experience the same discrimination against their grandchildren tomorrow”* (sondakika.com).

Eleventh statement: In a public statement by the Governorship of Aksaray it was announced that a Special Education School with 12 classrooms will be built in Aksaray: *“Special education students have been studying here for 5 years. The news with the title ‘Children with autism was booed in Aksaray’, which was published in some media organs, does not reflect the truth and children continue their normal education in their schools. A Special Education School with 12 classrooms has been planned in the 2020 investment program, and the necessary investigation has been started on the subject”* (kizlarsoruyor.com).

Twelfth statement: Justice and Development Party (AKP) Spokesperson Ömer Çelik also made a statement on Twitter, *“We carefully monitor the events that come to the agenda under the title of autism, which hurt our children with special educational needs and their precious families. There will be no disruption in the education of our children who need special education. Discrimination against them will not be allowed. It is essential that our children who need special education continue their education in the same environment with their peers”*. All children are one in universe. None of them can be separated from the other.” said Çelik and added, *“It is essential that all of our children receive education in a qualified environment and that children are not separated by any corridors or other practices. The sensitivity of our citizens from every segment and the media has proved this once again”* (iha.com.tr).

Thirteenth statement: On Wednesday, November 13, 2019, the Parliamentary Down Syndrome, Autism and Other Developmental Disorders Research Commission conducted an investigation at the school in Aksaray. The commission wanted the interview the headman as well, but the congressman could not reach him. Congressman of CHP from Kayseri, Çetin Arık, who is a member of the commission said, *“The headman avoided us, we couldn’t reach him”*. Arık stated that parents are separated among themselves as “them” and “us”. He said, *“It is a very sad situation. Even the door that kids*

go in and out of school is separate. They are completely separated under the name of inclusive education” (evrensel.net).

Arik stated that the families of children with autism are saying that the school administration and the headman of the neighborhood provoked the event and underlined that it is not enough to open an investigation only to the principal. Arik continued his speech as follows: *“Signatures were collected a year ago to expel these children from the school. Headman claimed that he will send these kids away from this school in his election campaign”*. Arik also said that the commission members asked Aksaray Governor Ali Manti to initiate an investigation against the headman and dismiss him. Arik added to his words: *“The headman committed discrimination and hate crimes” (evrensel.net).*

Fourteenth statement: Anadolu Autism Foundation President Nüvit Uyar evaluated the booing of children with autism at school: *“The children with autism and their parents are dealing with a lot of problems. The collective reaction in this case is an isolated event.”* The booing of the children with autism by parents who want the classes of the children with autism to be closed in Aksaray Mehmetçik Primary School attracted great public reaction. Nüvit Uyar, secretary of the Turkey Autism Council and president of Anadolu Autism Foundation, is also a father of a child with autism. Uyar stated that what have been revealed by this event is just the tip of the autism issue in Turkey and he stressed the need to look at the whole issue. Noting that the situation is not different in private schools and that some private schools don’t even accept the children with autism for different reasons, Uyar said, *“The children with autism and their parents are dealing with a lot of problems. The collective reaction in this case is an isolated event. What is isolated in this event is that parents with children in normal education collectively protested and booed the children with autism and unfortunately the school administration was also involved in this. This is the first thing I said here! There have been a lot of problems with children with autism in inclusive schools, but this is the first collective case. Therefore, the relevant authorities of the state should react in the most severe way and do whatever is required”*. Uyar stated that what have been revealed by this event is just the tip of the autism issue in Turkey and he stressed the need to look at the whole issue. He asked that relevant regulations should be made immediately in public and private schools. He said that Turkey Autism Council, representing more than a million children with autism and nearly 5 million families, through numerous meetings and workshops, made a report out of the Turkey autism action plan and added, *“This report is currently in Turkey Autism Research Commission. We are waiting for the necessary actions to be taken”*. Uyar said that there were thousands of cases against children with autism, one of which was the struggle that his friend Sedef Erken, who has fought a lot of battles in this field and couldn’t get her child accepted by schools, started against the private schools. Reminding that 350 thousand signatures were collected in that campaign, Uyar said, *“Why don’t they want her child? There is an erroneous prejudice that that child will somehow harm their own children and cause their education to fall behind. However, there are studies showing that representation of individuals with autism or individuals with disabilities in classes with normal populations with certain proportions can have positive effects on the normal group. On the other hand, it improves team spirit and improves the sense of benevolence. So, in essence, we are talking about being a human”*. Also referring to basic education in autism,

Uyar emphasized that this is called applied behavior analysis and that it should be given with full support by the state to the 0-6 age group. Noting that the current resource for this is 4 + 8 sessions per month, whereas the need for an autistic person is 80 sessions per month, Uyar said, *“In other words, the state is providing only one-tenth, one-eighth of what it should be providing. The resource of humans who are qualified to give this training is another problem. Let’s say that formal education starts at the age of 6, when you apply this behavioral school between 0-6 years old and the natural methods associated with it to a child with autism, roughly half of them can be integrated into normal education. The other half can be partially integrated to run their lives as independently as possible. The world is no longer about the separation and isolation of disabled people. This is especially true for autism; we are in a period where it is thought as right and humane for people with autism to take part in life in an integrated way”* (evrensel.net).

With their studies, scientists guide country administrators. All of those who are responsible, from local administrations to school administrations, and even those who rule are obliged to do whatever necessary. Among the people registered to “National People with Disabilities Database of Turkey” 66.9% percent expressed that sidewalks and crosswalks are not appropriate for them. Within the scope of the protocol signed with Administration on Disabled People, Turkey Statistical Institute announced the results of “Problems and Expectations of Disabled People Survey, 2010” conducted on disabled people registered in National People with Disabilities Database of Turkey. The aim of this survey, which was conducted countrywide for the first time, was to determine the problems and expectations of people with disabilities in their daily lives to effectively establish policies in this area. The framework of the survey was “National People with Disabilities Database of Turkey” and it was conducted in June 2010. According to the report, among those who are registered in the database 29.2% have mental disabilities, 25.6% have continuing disabilities, 8.8% have orthopedic disabilities, 8.4% have visual disabilities, 5.9% have auditory disabilities, 3.9% have emotional disabilities, 0.2% have language and speech disabilities, and 18% have multiple disabilities. 58.6% of the registered people are male and 41.4% are female. 56.8% have acquired their disability as a result of an illness. 15.9% have “genetic or hereditary disorders”, 9.6% have disabilities acquired due to “accidents”, and 3% have disabilities acquired due to “problems during pregnancy or childbirth”. According to the report, 66.9% percent of the registered people with disabilities expressed that sidewalks and crosswalks are not appropriate for them. Regarding the physical environment arrangement of their place of living, 66.3% of the registered people with disabilities stated that the building they live in, 55.4% stated that shops, markets and restaurants, 58.4% stated that public buildings, 55.4% stated that post offices, banks and similar places are not appropriate for people with disabilities. 38.4% of the people with disabilities are regularly benefiting from social aids. Among these, 27% regularly benefit from pension for disabled people and 11.2% benefit from aids given in kind and financial aids given by General Directorate of Social Assistance and Solidarity. 55.7% of the people with disabilities expressed that they don’t want to have jobs that require heavy physical work. 33.3% expressed that due to their health complications they want to be able to use small breaks more frequently, and 27.7% expressed that they want

to work part time. 85.7% of the registered people with disabilities asked for increased social assistance and support. 77% wanted improved health services, 40.4% wanted improved and widespread care services, 28.7% wanted improved job opportunities, 25.6% wanted improved educational opportunities, and 17.7% wanted improved regulations on physical environment and transportation opportunities (haberler.com).

4. Results

With this study titled “Why is it hard to be different?”, the reasons of the incident occurred in the city of Aksaray, the responsible people for this incident, and solutions to the problems were examined. As a result, in the light of explanations, the process that started with the published news was ignored by the governorship. They claimed that no such incident happened. The department of communication is trying to dictate what the media can or cannot write when reporting such issues. The state does not want the public to know what has happened. Members of the parliamentary research commission went to the scene and exchanged opinions with the parties, emphasized the lack of inclusive education and the right to education, and pointed out those who failed their responsibilities. With his every statement, the headman of the neighborhood took an active role in the alienating process of students with disabilities by the governor's office, the school principal and the school family union. They are fine with students who have mild disabilities, but they don't want children with heavy disabilities to attend their schools. Parents with disabled children are always forced to fight for their rights. The Ministry of National Education expresses the problems in the educational system in their workshops. In practice, the solution of the problem is spread throughout the process. Considering that the Minister of National Education is a special education specialist, such problems should be solved more easily. The ruling party's spokesperson speaks the right words about education and training for the disabled, but it is in the hands of the government to correct the practice.

People are alienating those who are different from them. Examples of such alienations include seculars vs. conservatives, alevi vs. sunni, women who wear hijab vs. women who don't wear hijab, and people with disabilities vs. people without disabilities. We believe that the reasons for this alienation should be examined in all stages of education, in advertisements and news in media, and in TV series and movies, and we believe that there should be educational and instructive approaches.

It is observed that individuals with special needs are successful in educational arrangements made in the least restricted environments. For inclusion to be effective, well-planned studies should be conducted on the preparation of the community, families, children and school administrators and teachers. Sherrill (1988) emphasizes that the morally correct approach is teaching disabled and non-disabled individuals to interact and understand each other. According to Mahon et al. (2000), inclusion is a process in which individuals with and without disability come together, and meaningful social interactions are developed and maintained. This process is important not only for individuals to live in a society, but also to be members of the society in which they live.

In the Special Education Services Regulation introduced in 2006 in our country, education through inclusion is defined as special education practices based on the principle that individuals who need special education should continue their education in public and private pre-schools, primary education, secondary education and non-formal education institutions with their peers without disability by providing support education services. The realization of educational practices through inclusion is possible with the presence of qualified teachers, school administrators and boards that will supervise them. Inclusive and special education should be carried out by ensuring that teachers with field education are appointed. It is not possible to get desired results in special education with paid or temporary teachers, or with teachers who are not specialized in this field. As seen in the last case study, inclusive education in primary schools cannot be applied successfully due to inadequacy and negative attitudes of teachers assigned to the education of children with disabilities.

The school principal and the vice principle, who were responsible for the booing of students with autism in Aksaray in November 18, 2019 were dismissed from their administrative positions. <https://www.aa.com.tr> Head of the neighborhood, Provincial Director of National Education, Governor, Minister of National Education, and Director of Communication may not be able to continue their duties after this event with peace of mind.

During the writing of this article, images of an inclusive student being beaten by his teacher in Ankara have emerged on social media and the teacher was suspended from duty. Knowing means having responsibility.

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